

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

25 Years of Cardiac Ion Channel QSAR: From hERG Dominance to Multi-Channel Modelling

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1. Supporting Tables

1.1. Studies

Table S1. Summary of surveyed studies on cardiac ion channels.

No.	Study (Year)	Study type	Models	Features	Channel
1.	Cavalli (2002) ¹	Pharm	PLS	3D Shape-based	hERG
2.	Ekins (2002) ²	Pharm	Alignment-based	3D Shape-based (CATALYST)	hERG
3.	Roche (2002) ³	Reg	SOM, PCA, PLS, NN	MD (VolSurf, DRAGON)	hERG
4.	Ekins (2003) ⁴	Pharm	Alignment-based	3D Shape-based (CATALYST)	hERG
5.	Keserü (2003) ⁵	Reg	LR + hQSAR	MD (VolSurf, Sybyl)	hERG
6.	Pearlstein (2003) ⁶	Pharm	3D Shape-based	Pharmacophore	hERG
7.	Aptula (2004) ⁷	Reg	MLR	MD, Quantum Chemical	hERG
8.	Aronov (2004) ⁸	BC	DT	Pharmacophore-based	hERG
9.	Bains (2004) ⁹	BC	DT	MD, Fragment-based	hERG
10.	Fioravanzo (2004) ¹⁰	BC	PLS	MD (DRAGON), EVA (from IR and Raman spectra), DRAGON	hERG
11.	Cianchetta (2005) ¹¹	Reg	PLS + hQSAR	3D Shape-based	hERG
12.	O'Brien (2005) ¹²	BC	NN, NB	Topological, Fragment-based, Circular	hERG
13.	Tobita (2005) ¹³	BC	SVM	MD (MOE), MACCS	hERG
14.	Aronov (2006) ¹⁴	Pharm	Alignment-based	3D Shape-based (MOE)	hERG
15.	Coi (2006) ¹⁵	Reg	LR	MD (CODESSA)	hERG
16.	Dubus (2006) ¹⁶	MC	DT	MD (MOE)	hERG
17.	Ekins (2006) ¹⁷	Reg	DT, SOM, Sammon Maps	MD (Smart Mining)	hERG
18.	Gepp (2006) ¹⁸	BC	DT	MD, QC (VAMP), Custom SMARTS	hERG
19.	Seierstad (2006) ¹⁹	Reg	MLP	MD (MOE), Topological (KH, GC), Atom Pairs, Fragment (ISIDA)	hERG
20.	Sun (2006) ²⁰	BC	NB	Atom Types, Circular	hERG
21.	Song (2006) ²¹	Reg	SVM, PLS, RF	Fragment (Clark 2005)	hERG
22.	Yoshida (2006) ²²	Reg	LR	MD	hERG
23.	Du (2007) ²³	Reg	PLS	Docking scores	hERG
24.	Leong (2007) ²⁴	Reg	SVM	Pharmacophore	hERG
25.	Obrezanova (2007) ²⁵	Reg	GP	MD (in-house), custom SMARTS	hERG
26.	Chekmarev (2008) ²⁶	BC	kNN, SVM, SOM	3D Shape-based	hERG
27.	Gunturi (2008) ²⁷	Reg	kNN, LOESS	MD (BioSuite, SYBYL)	hERG
28.	Jia (2008) ²⁸	BC	SVM	Atom Types	hERG
29.	Kramer (2008) ²⁹	Reg	MLR, PLS, SVR	MD and QC	hERG
30.	Li (2008) ³⁰	BC	SVM	Field-based	hERG
31.	Thai [◊] (2008) ³¹	BC	NB	MD	hERG
32.	Thai [◊] (2008) ³²	BC	PLS, CP-NN	MD (MOE)	hERG
33.	Wang (2008) ³³	BC	DT, MLP, RBFNetwork, SVM, LR	3D MD, QC	hERG
34.	Coi (2009) ³⁴	BC	MLR	MD (CODESSA), QC (MOPAC)	hERG
35.	Ermondi (2009) ³⁵	Reg	PLS	Field-based	hERG
36.	Hansen (2009) ³⁶	Reg	RF, SVR, GP, RidgeReg	MD (MOE), Field-based, Pharmacophore	hERG
37.	Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁷	BC	SVM	Fragment	hERG
38.	Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁸	BC	kNN	Circular, Fragment, 3D-shape based	hERG
39.	Thai (2009) ³⁹	BC	PLS, NB, CP-NN	MD (MOE, VolSurf), SIBAR	hERG

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No.	Study (Year)	Study type	Models	Features	Channel
40.	Doddareddy (2010) ⁴⁰	BC	LDA, SVM	Circular	hERG
41.	Obrezanova (2010) ⁴¹	BC	GP, DT, SVM, RF, PLS	MD (in-house), custom SMARTS	hERG
42.	Su (2010) ⁴²	BC, Reg	PLS	4D-FP (MDDM), MD (MOE)	hERG
43.	Wiśniowska (2010) ⁴³	BC	RF	MD, Circular, Experimental	hERG
44.	Cuny (2011) ⁴⁴	BC, Reg	kNN, PLS	MD (MOE), Pharmacophore	hERG
45.	Kim (2011) ⁴⁵	BC	NB, RF	MD, Circular	hERG
46.	Obiol-Pardo (2011) ⁴⁶	Reg	PLS	Field-based, Docking Scores	hERG, Kv7.1
47.	Robinson (2011) ⁴⁷	BC	SVM, RF	MD (MOE), Circular	hERG
48.	Sinha (2011) ⁴⁸	Reg	MLR	MD	hERG
49.	Shen (2011) ⁴⁹	BC	SVM	4D-FP (MDDM), MD (MOE, VolSurf)	hERG
50.	Broccatelli (2012) ⁵⁰	BC	PLS, LDA, SVM, RF, kNN	MD (MOE, DRAGON, CDK), Field-based (VS+), Interaction (FLAP), Fragment	hERG
51.	Kar (2012) ⁵¹	BC, Reg	LDA, PLS	MD (PaDEL, Cerius2, DRAGON)	hERG
52.	Polak (2012) ⁵²	Reg	MLP, NFS, SMO, RF	MD (ChemAxon)	Kv7.1
53.	Tan (2012) ⁵³	BC, Reg	PLS	MD (CODESSA), QC (MOPAC), Pharmacophore	hERG
54.	Wang (2012) ⁵⁴	BC	NB	Circular, Path-based	hERG
55.	Wiśniowska (2012) ⁵⁵	Reg	MLP, MON-MLP, NFS	MD (ChemAxon)	Cav1.2
56.	Czodrowski (2013) ⁵⁶	BC	RF	MD (RDKit)	hERG
57.	Kireeva (2013) ⁵⁷	BC	GTM, SVM	Fragment (IPLF), Path-based (CDK)	hERG
58.	Braga (2014) ⁵⁸	BC	SVM, RF, GBM, DT	Circular, Fragment (MACCS, PubChem), Pharmacophore	hERG
59.	Kratz (2014) ⁵⁹	BC	Alignment-based	Pharmacophore (LigandScout, StudioCatalyst)	hERG
60.	Liu (2014) ⁶⁰	BC	NB	MD, Circular	hERG
61.	Braga (2015) ⁶¹	BC, MC	SVM	Circular, Path-based (CDK)	hERG
62.	Du (2015) ⁶²	Reg	Winnow, SVM	MD, Circular	hERG
63.	Ma (2015) ⁶³	Reg	RF, SVM, DNN, GBM, GP	MD, Circular, Fragment (MACCS), AtomPairs	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
64.	Chavan (2016) ⁶⁴	BC	kNN	Path-based (CDK), Topological (EState), Fragment (MACCS, PubChem, SubFP)	hERG
65.	Didziapetris (2016) ⁶⁵	BC	GBM	Topological, Physicochemical	hERG
66.	Gobbi (2016) ⁶⁶	Reg	LR	String-fragment	hERG
67.	Sheridan (2016) ⁶⁷	Reg	XGB	Atom Pairs, Donor-Acceptor Pairs	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
68.	Wang (2016) ⁶⁸	BC	NB, SVM	Pharmacophore (DS2.5)	hERG
69.	Zhang (2016) ⁶⁹	BC	SVM, NB, kNN, RF, DT	MD (PaDEL), Path-based (CDK), Fragment (MACCS, PubChem, SubFP)	hERG
70.	Chemi (2017) ⁷⁰	Reg	PLS	Pharmacophore	hERG
71.	Li (2017) ⁷¹	BC	kNN, SVM, MLR, PLS, RF, DT	MD (DRAGON, ChemAxon), Path-based (CDK), Topological (EState), Fragment (ISIDA, SA, GSfrag, SiRMS), 3D (Inductive, Mera and Mersy, Adriana, Spectrophores), String-based (QNPR)	hERG
72.	Sun (2017) ⁷²	BC	SVC	Atom Types	hERG
73.	Alves (2018) ⁷³	BC	kNN	MD (PaDEL, DRAGON), Circular, Fragment (SiRMS)	hERG
74.	Munawar (2018) ⁷⁴	Reg	PLS	Field-based (GRIND)	hERG
75.	Siramshetty (2018) ⁷⁵	BC	kNN, SVM, RF	Circular, Fragment (MACCS, PubChem)	hERG
76.	Wacker (2018) ⁷⁶	BC, Reg	XGB, RF	MD (RDKit), Pharmacophore	hERG
77.	Yang (2018) ⁷⁷	N/A	RF, SVM, kNN	Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Atom Pairs	hERG

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No.	Study (Year)	Study type	Models	Features	Channel
78.	Cai (2019) ⁷⁸	BC	DNN, NB, SVM, RF, GCN	MD (MOE), Embedding (Mol2Vec)	hERG
79.	Hu (2019) ⁷⁹	BC	GCN, RF	Circular, Graphs	hERG
80.	Konda (2019) ⁸⁰	BC	RF, MLP, SMO	MD (PaDEL)	hERG
81.	Lee (2019) ⁸¹	BC	LR, LogReg, Ridge, NN, NB, RF	MD (DRAGON), Circular	hERG
82.	Munawar (2019) ⁸²	Reg	PLS	Interaction-based (PLIF)	hERG
83.	Negami (2019) ⁸³	Reg	LR	FEP-based (MP-CAFEE)	hERG
84.	Ogura (2019) ⁸⁴	BC	SVM	MD (MOE, PipelinePilot), Circular	hERG
85.	Zhang (2019) ⁸⁵	BC	RF, DNN	MD (ChemoPy, MOE, PaDEL)	hERG
86.	Choi (2020) ⁸⁶	Reg	ANN, NB, SVM, RF	Circular, Path-based (CDK)	hERG
87.	Khalifa (2020) ⁸⁷	BC, Reg	BayesNet, NB, MLP, K-Star, RF, SVM, SGD, SMO, GP, GLM, GBM, FFNN	Path-based (CDK), Topological (EState), Fragment (MACCS, PubChem, SubFP, Klek), Atom Pairs	Nav1.5
88.	Kim (2020) ⁸⁸	BC	Self-attention DNN	Circular	hERG
89.	Liu (2020) ⁸⁹	BC	SVM, RF, XGB	Atom Pairs, Topological (EState), Fragment (MACCS, Klek, PubChem), Path-based (FP4, FP4C), MD (PaDEL)	hERG
90.	Ryu (2020) ⁹⁰	BC	Ensemble: DNN, GCN	MD (Mordred), Circular, Fragment (PubChem), Graphs	hERG
91.	Siramshetty (2020) ⁹¹	BC	RF, XGB, FFNN, LSTM	MD (RDKit), Circular, Embedding (AE)	hERG
92.	Wang (2020) ⁹²	BC	Conv-CapsNet, RBM	MD, Fragment (MACCS)	hERG
93.	Creanza (2021) ⁹³	BC	LASSO-SVM	Docking Scores (GLIDE, GOLD), Interactions (PLIF)	hERG
94.	Karim (2021) ⁹⁴	BC	(DNN + GCN + Conv1D) > DNN	MD (Mordred), Circular, Embeddings (Smi2Vec, FP2Vec), Fragment (PubChem), Graph	hERG
95.	Lee (2021) ⁹⁵	BC, Reg	XGB, RF	MD (RDKit), Pharmacophore	hERG
96.	Meng (2021) ⁹⁶	BC	SVR, RF, kNN, MLP, BRR	Interaction, Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Topological (EState)	hERG
97.	Moorthy (2021) ⁹⁷	BC	DT, RF, SVM, NB	MD (MOE), Fragment (MACCS)	hERG
98.	Sato (2021) ⁹⁸	BC	SVM, RF, MLP	MD (RDKit, Mordred), Path-based (CDK), Circular	hERG
99.	Stergiopoulos (2021) ⁹⁹	Reg	Stepwise Regression	MD, Experimental ($\alpha - 1 - acid - GP$ binding, IAM permeability)	hERG
100.	Wu (2021) ¹⁰⁰	BC, Reg	MT-GAT	Graphs	hERG
101.	Xiong (2021) ¹⁰¹	BC	MT-GAT	Graphs	hERG
102.	Arab (2022) ¹⁰²	MC	SVM, RF, MLP	MD (PaDEL)	hERG, Nav1.5
103.	Delre (2022) ¹⁰³	BC	RF, KNN, GBM, XGB, SVM	MD (DRAGON)	hERG
104.	Ding (2022) ¹⁰⁴	BC	GBM, RF, SVM, kNN	MD, Circular, 3D Shape-based, 4D Dynamics-based	hERG
105.	Ishihara (2022) ¹⁰⁵	BC	XGB, NB, SVM, RF, ANN	MD (RDKit, Mordred)	hERG
106.	Kim (2022) ¹⁰⁶	BC, Reg	D-MPNN > Attn. Pool > DNN	Graphs	hERG
107.	Kong (2022) ¹⁰⁷	BC	LogReg, SVM, NB, MLP, RF	Path-based (CDK), Topological (EState), Fragment (MACCS, PubChem)	Nav1.5
108.	Krishna (2022) ¹⁰⁸	BC, Reg	DT, NN, SVM, RF, LDA, DNN	MD (RDKit, OPERA)	hERG
109.	Lanevskij (2022) ¹⁰⁹	BC, Reg	XGB (with AFT)	MD	hERG
110.	Melnikov (2022) ¹¹⁰	BC	XGB	MD (RDKit), Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Topological Torsion	hERG
111.	Shan (2022) ¹¹¹	BC	D-MPNN	MD (RDKit, MOE), Circular, Fragment (MACCS, PubChem), Embedding (Mol2Vec)	hERG

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No.	Study (Year)	Study type	Models	Features	Channel
112.	Zhang (2022) ¹¹²	BC	FFNN, RF, XGB	Circular, Fragment (MACCS)	hERG
113.	Arab (2023) ¹¹³	BC	(DNN + GCN) > DNN	MD (Mordred), Circular, Fragment (PubChem), Graphs	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
114.	Banerjee (2023) ¹¹⁴	BC, Reg	PLS RASAR, Ridge, SVM, RF, GBM, ADA, MLP, kNN	MD, Similarity (RASAR)	hERG
115.	Chen (2023) ¹¹⁵	BC	Graph, kNN, SVM, RF, NN	MD (RDKit), Circular, Atom Pairs, Fragment (MACCS), Topological Torsion	hERG
116.	Das (2023) ¹¹⁶	BC, Reg	DT, RF, LogReg, AdaBoost, kNN, SVM, NB, NN, SGD	MD (PaDEL), Path-based (CDK)	hERG
117.	Feng (2023) ¹¹⁷	BC	DT, DNN	3D Shape-based, Embedding (CDDD, Transformer)	hERG
118.	Wang ^o (2023) ¹¹⁸	BC	(DNN + GAT) > DNN	Path-based (CDK), Circular, Fragment (PubChem), Atom Pairs, SMILES	hERG
119.	Wang ^o (2023) ¹¹⁹	BC	GCN, GSTN, SVM	Circular, Graphs	hERG
120.	Vittorio (2023) ¹²⁰	BC	RF	MD, Circular	hERG
121.	Ylipää (2023) ¹²¹	BC	RF, XGB, SVM, DNN, GRU-DNN, MP-GNN	MD (Mordred), Graphs, SMILES	hERG
122.	Arab (2024) ¹²²	BC	RF	MD (Mordred), Circular, Fragment (PubChem)	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
123.	Chen (2024) ¹²³	BC	DNN	Fragment (MACCS)	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
124.	He (2024) ¹²⁴	BC	RoBERTa emb. > MLP	SMILES	hERG
125.	Liu (2024) ¹²⁵	BC	kNN, SVM, RF, MLP, LSTM, AE	MD (Mold2)	hERG
126.	Sanches (2024) ¹²⁶	BC, MC, Reg	RF, kNN, SVM, LGBM, XGB	Circular	hERG
127.	Wang (2024) ¹²⁷	BC	(GIN + DNN) > Attention > DNN	Circular, Fragment (MACCS, PubChem), Graphs, Embedding (Smi2Vec), Pharmacophore	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
128.	Yang (2024) ¹²⁸	BC	GNN + Attn	Graphs	hERG
129.	Cano (2025) ¹²⁹	BC	XGB Ensemble	MD (MOE, alvaDesc), Topological (Kappa), Circular, Fragment (MACCS)	hERG
130.	Feng (2025) ¹³⁰	BC	(GIN + BiGRU + MLP) > Attn	Circular, Fragment (PubChem, MACCS), Graphs, SMILES, Pharmacophore	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
131.	Gambacorta (2025) ¹³¹	BC	RF, SVM, XGB, kNN, ADA	Fragment (CSFP)	ERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
132.	Han (2025) ¹³²	BC	40 models from HyperOPT-sklearn	Circular	hERG
133.	Hossain (2025) ¹³³	BC	Logic Tensor Network	MD (Morgan), Path-based (CDK), Embeddings (MegaMolBART, LLaMA3.2, Gemini, QWEN1.5b)	hERG
134.	Jin (2025) ¹³⁴	BC	((GNN > Transformer) + MLP) > Attn > MLP	MD, Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Graphs, Path-based (RDKit)	hERG
135.	Jing (2025) ¹³⁵	BC	DNN, GNN, RF, GBM, SVM, NB, kNN, MLP	MD, Atom Types (AMBER), Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Atom Pairs, Topological Torsion	hERG
136.	Kyro (2025) ¹³⁶	BC, Reg, Gen	(DNN + GAT) > DNN	MD (RDKit), Circular, Graphs, Embeddings (BDT)	hERG, Nav1.5, Cav1.2
137.	Lee (2025) ¹³⁷	BC	(GAT + MLP) > FCNN	MD, Circular, Graphs	hERG
138.	Liu ^o (2025) ¹³⁸	BC	NB, RF, SVM, kNN, XGB, Transformer	MD (RDKit), Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Atom Pairs, Path-based (FP2)	hERG
139.	Liu ^o (2025) ¹³⁹	BC, Reg	FCNN, Conv2D + DenseNet, EqGAT	Circular, Graphs, Images	hERG
140.	Mohammad (2025) ¹⁴⁰	BC	RF, XGB, MLP, SVM, kNN, DT	MD (RDKit, Avalon), Path-based (CDK), Embeddings (Mol2Vec), Fragment (MACCS, Klek), Atom Pair	hERG
141.	Tran-Nguyen (2025) ¹⁴¹	BC	RF, XGB, DNN	Interaction (PLEC)	hERG
142.	Xu (2025) ¹⁴²	BC	XGB	Various (RDKit, DeepChem, MolMap, Mordred)	hERG

Table S1 – continued from previous page

No.	Study (Year)	Study type	Models	Features	Channel
143.	Yang (2025) ¹⁴³	BC	RF, SVM, GBM, LogReg	Circular	hERG
144.	Zhang (2025) ¹⁴⁴	BC	Ridge, Lasso, RF, XGB, kNN, GNN	MD (Avalon), Circular, Fragment (MACCS), Graphs	hERG
145.	Chu (2026) ¹⁴⁵	BC	(ViT + (GIN > GAT) + AE) > MoE Attention > DNN	Images, Graphs, Circular, Pharmacophore	hERG
146.	Zhao (2026) ¹⁴⁶	BC	RF, GBM, SVM, MPNN, GCN, CNN, Transformer	MD (Mordred), Circular, Fragment (MACCS, Pub- Chem), Graphs, SMILES, Interaction (PLIF)	hERG

Symbol explanations: ◊ separate studies

Study type abbreviations: BC - Binary Classification, MC - Multi-Class Classification, Reg - Regression, Pharm - Pharmacophore, Gen - Generative modelling

Model abbreviations: ADA - ADaptive Boosting, AE - Auto Encoder, AFT - Accelerated Failure Time, BDT - BiDirectional Transformer, BRR - Bayesian Ridge Regression, CPNN - CounterPropagation Neural Network, DNN - Deep neural Network, DT - Decision Tree, FCNN - Fully Connected Neural Network, FFNN - FeedForward Neural Network, GAT - Graph Attention Transformer, GBM - Gradient Boosting Machine, GCN - Graph Convolution Network, GIN - Graph Isomorphism Network, GLM - Generalized Linear Model, GP - Gaussian Process, GRU - Gated Recurrent Unit, GSTN - Graph Substructure Transformer Network, GTM - Generative Topological Maps, hQSAR - hologram QSAR, kNN - k-Nearest Neighbors, LDA - Linear Discriminant Analysis, LGBM - Light Gradient Boosting Machine, LR - Linear Regression, LSTM - Long-Short Term Memory, MLP - Multi-Layer Perceptron, MLR - Multiple Linear Regression, MoE - Mixture of Experts, MON-MLP - Monotone Multi-Layer Perceptron, MT - Multi Task, NB - Naive Bayes, NFS - Neuro-Fuzzy Systems, NN - Neural Network, PCA - Principal Component Analysis, PLS - Partial Least Squares, RBM - Restricted Boltzmann Machines, SGD - Stochastic Gradient Descent, SMO - Sequential Minimal Optimization, SOM - Self Organizing Maps (also known as Kohonen Maps), SVM - Support Vector Machines, ViT - Vision Transformer, XGB - eXtreme Gradient Boosting

Features abbreviations: CDDD - Continuous and Data-Driven Descriptors, CSFP - Core Substituent Fingerprints, EVA - EigenVAlue, FEP - Free Energy Perturbation, FLAP - Fingerprints for Ligands and Proteins, FP4 - Fingerprint 4, GCAT - Gose-Crippen Atom Types, GRIND - GRid INdependent Descriptors, IAM - Immobilized Artificial Membrane, IPLF - ISIDA Property-Labelled Fragment descriptors, KH - Kier-Hall Indices, MACCS - Molecular ACCes System, MD - Molecular Descriptors, MDDM - Molecular Distance-Dependent Matrix, PLIF - Protein-Ligand Interaction Fingerprints, QC - Quantum Chemical descriptors, QNPR - Quantitative Name-Property Relationship, RASAR - Read-Across Structure-Activity Relationship, SA - Structural Alerts, SIBAR - SIMilarity BAsed descriptors, SiRMS - Simplex Representation of Molecular Structure

Software: Avalon, BioSuite, CDK, Cerius2, ChemAxon, CODESSA, DRAGON, ISIDA, Ligand Scout, MOE, Mold2, MOPAC, PaDEL, PipelinePilot, Smart Mining, Studio Catalyst, Sybyl, VolSurf

1.2. Datasets

Table S2. Overview of publicly available datasets used for cardiac ion channel QSAR modelling. The Size column indicates the total number of compounds available as of February 2026. Links to currently accessible resources are listed in Table S3. In the Sources column, *Literature* denotes primary experimental publications, whereas Study denotes previously published cardiac ion channel QSAR studies included in this review.

Study (Year)	Size	No. Toxic	Data Type	Availability	Sources
Ponti (2001) ¹⁴⁷	137	N/A	IC50	In paper ^{§†}	Literature
Cavalli (2002) ¹	37	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ¹⁴⁷ , FenichelDB
Roche (2002) ³	472	N/A	IC50	In paper [†]	In-house Roche, known drugs
Ekins (2002) ²	22	N/A	IC50	In paper	In-house ElliLilly
Keserü (2003) ⁵	68	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ³ , FenichelDB
Pearlstein (2003) ⁶	23	N/A	IC50	In paper	In-house Aventis Pharma
Aronov (2004) ⁸	414	85@40 μ M	Binary	Online	Studies ^{1,2} , FenichelDB, Literature
Aptula (2004) ⁷	19	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ⁶ , Literature
Bains (2004) ⁹	124	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Fioravanzo (2004) ¹⁰	70	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Cianchetta (2005) ¹¹	882	546@10 μ M	IC50	SI [†]	Studies ^{1,6} , In-house Sanofi
Tobita (2005) ¹³	73	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Coi (2006) ¹⁵	82	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ⁹ , Literature
Ekins (2006) ¹⁷	134	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ² , Literature
Seierstad (2006) ¹⁹	439	N/A	IC50	In paper [†]	In-house J&J
Song (2006) ²¹	90	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{1,2} , In-house Locus, Literature
Sun (2006) ²⁰	1979	N/A	IC50	In paper [†]	Study ⁵ , In-house Roche
Yoshida (2006) ²²	104	N/A	IC50	In paper	Studies ^{2,6} , FenichelDB, Literature
Du (2007) ²³	56	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Leong (2007) ²⁴	39	N/A	IC50	In paper	Studies ^{1-3,6,9,20} , Literature
Obrezanova (2007) ²⁵	137	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{2,6} , FenichelDB, Literature
Gunturi (2008) ²⁷	165	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ²² , Literature
Kramer (2008) ²⁹	113	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{2,6} , FenichelDB, PubChem, Literature
Li (2008) ³⁰	495	N/A	Binary	SI	Studies ^{1,2,5,6,8,9,11,13,19,21} , FenichelDB, Literature
Thai [◊] (2008) ³¹	313	197@10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{2,3,5-7,9,11,21} , FenichelDB, Literature
Thai [◊] (2008) ³²	285	195<10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{2,3,5-13,16-18,20,21,30,31} , FenichelDB, Literature
Coi (2009) ³⁴	155	N/A	IC50	In paper	Studies ^{2,6} , Literature
Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁷	242	138@10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{1,5,9,17,21,22,31} , Literature
Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁸	275	160<10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{1,5,9,17,21,22,29,31} , Literature
Polak (2009) ¹⁴⁸	201	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ³ , FenichelDB, QTDrugs
Thai (2009) ³⁹	307	N/A	Mixed	SI	Studies ^{2,3,5-7,9,11,21} , FenichelDB, Literature
Doddareddy (2010) ⁴⁰	2644	1112<10 μ M	Binary	SI	Studies ^{13,15,25,30} , Literature
Obrezanova (2010) ⁴¹	168	117@10 μ M	Binary	SI	Study ²⁵ , Literature
Su (2010) ⁴²	250	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{21,22,30,31}
Cuny (2011) ⁴⁴	529	178	IC50	In paper [†]	Studies ^{5,6,17,20-22,147} , DrugBank, Literature
Obiol-Pardo (2011) ⁴⁶	355 (hERG) 162 (KCNQ1)	N/A	IC50	SI	Literature
Robinson (2011) ⁴⁷	220	N/A	IC50	SI	Literature
Sinha (2011) ⁴⁸	157	N/A	IC50	In paper	Studies ^{2,6,10,11,15,19,21,30}
Broccatelli (2012) ⁵⁰	1051	185<1 μ M	IC50	SI	ChEMBL, Tox-Portal

Table S2 – continued from previous page

Study (Year)	Size	No. Toxic	Data Type	Availability	Sources
Polak (2012) ⁵²	98	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Tan (2012) ⁵³	113	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Wang (2012) ⁵⁴	806	N/A	IC50	From ⁶⁸	Studies ^{3,13,21,23,25,30,31,37,41,148} , WOMBAT, Literature
Wiśniewska (2012) ⁵⁵	123	N/A	IC50	In paper	Literature
Czodrowski (2013) ⁵⁶	4415	3047@10 μ M	Binary [‡]	SI	ChEMBL
Braga (2015) ⁶¹	5984	2565<10 μ M	Binary [‡]	GitHub [¶]	ChEMBL
Du (2015) ⁶²	306895	N/A	%Inh [‡]	SI, Online	MLSMR collection
Chavan (2016) ⁶⁴	172	93@10 μ M	IC50	SI	FenichelDB, OCHEM
Didziapetris (2016) ⁶⁵	6690	3908@10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{40,50,148} , ChEMBL, Literature
Wang (2016) ⁶⁸	806	N/A	IC50	SI	Study ⁵⁴
Zhang (2016) ⁶⁹	1570	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{40,54} , ChEMBL, hERGCentral
Chemi (2017) ⁷⁰	421	22<50nM	IC50	SI	Literature
Sun (2017) ⁷²	3024	1008@30 μ M	IC50	SI	qHTS Thalium Flux assay
Munawar (2018) ⁷⁴	207	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{29,148} , ChEMBL, FenichelDB
Sato (2018) ¹⁴⁹	291219	9890@10 μ M	Binary	From ^{111,117,129†}	Databases ^{150–153}
Siramshetty (2018) ⁷⁵	5804	4096@10 μ M	Binary [‡]	GitHub	Studies ^{30,40,47,72} , ChEMBL
Cai (2019) ⁷⁸	7889	4355@10 μ M	Binary [‡]	SI	Studies ^{40,65,68,70} , ChEMBL
Konda (2019) ⁸⁰	8705	5286@10 μ M	IC50	SI	ChEMBL
Zhang(2019) ⁸⁵	697	211@5 μ M	Binary	SI	Studies ^{30,64} , PubChem
Choi (2020) ⁸⁶	5299	3735<1 μ M	IC50	SI	ChEMBL, Literature
Khalifa (2020) ⁸⁷	2596 (Nav1.5) 714 (Nav1.5)	N/A	IC50 Inhibition	SI	ChEMBL, BindingDB, In-house Jubilant BioSys
Ryu (2020) ⁹⁰	14440	6632@10 μ M	N/A	From ^{87†}	Studies ^{31,40,65,74,78} , ChEMBL, BindingDB, In-house
Siramshetty (2020) ⁹¹	8984	2230	Binary	GitHub	ChEMBL, PubChem, In-house NCATS
Creanza (2021) ⁹³	8337	1308<1 μ M	IC50	SI	ChEMBL
Lee (2021) ⁹⁵	3448 678	N/A	IC50 Ki	GitHub	ChEMBL
Meng(2021) ⁹⁶	9215	N/A	IC50	SI	ChEMBL
Moorthy (2021) ⁹⁷	136*	N/A	IC50	SI	Literature
Stergiopoulos (2021) ⁹⁹	90	N/A	IC50	In paper	Study ¹⁴⁹
Wu (2021) ¹⁰⁰	1565	955@10 μ M	Binary [‡]	GitHub	Literature
Arab (2022) ¹⁰²	8930 (hERG) 1767 (Nav1.5)	N/A	IC50	GitHub	Study ⁸⁰ , ChEMBL, PubChem
Delre (2022) ¹⁰³	8755	N/A	IC50	GitHub	ChEMBL
Ding (2022) ¹⁰⁴	7836	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{65,82} , ChEMBL
Kim (2022) ¹⁰⁶	304045 14322	N/A	IC50	GitHub	Study ⁶²
Krishna (2022) ¹⁰⁸	8311	8488@10 μ M	Binary	SI	Study ⁷⁸ , Databases ^{150,152,154}
Lanevskij (2022) ¹⁰⁹	9311	1970@1 μ M	IC50	SI	ChEMBL, Tox21 ¹⁵⁵
Zhang (2022) ¹¹²	9311 12850	4862@10 μ M	IC50	SI	Study ⁶⁵ , Literature
	22246 (hERG)	6907@10 μ M	Binary	Online	Study ⁷² , ChEMBL, Literature
Arab (2023) ¹¹³	2069 (Nav1.5) 802 (Cav1.2)	N/A	IC50	Zenodo	Studies ^{40,65,80,82} , Databases ^{150,152–154} , U.S. Patents
Banerjee (2023) ¹¹⁴	261	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{17,51,99}
Chen (2023) ¹¹⁵	4556	N/A	IC50	SI	Studies ^{40,69} , ChEMBL
Das (2023) ¹¹⁶	6766	4000@10 μ M	IC50	SI	Studies ^{1,13,28,31,35,48}

Table S2 – continued from previous page

Study (Year)	Size	No. Toxic	Data Type	Availability	Sources
Wang (2023) (CBM) ¹¹⁸	10355	4479@10 μ M	Binary	GitHub	Studies ^{80,82,83,89} , ChEMBL
Vittorio (2023) ¹²⁰	12789	N/A	pK	Zenodo	ChEMBL, GOSTAR
Sanches (2024) ¹²⁶	7307	3731@10 μ M	Binary	SI	ChEMBL
	6142	N/A	4-class		
Yang (2024) ¹²⁸	4315		IC50	GitHub	Study ¹⁰⁶ , ChEMBL, PubChem
	14322	8488@10 μ M	Binary		
Gambacorta (2025) ¹³¹	10035 (hERG)	5042@10 μ M	IC50	GitHub	ChEMBL
	1436 (Nav1.5)	679@10 μ M			
Han (2025) ¹³²	734 (Cav1.2)	405@10 μ M	Binary	GitHub	ChEMBL
	6744	3465@10 μ M			
Hossain (2025) ¹³³	20409	9826@10 μ M	Binary	GitHub	Studies ^{68,94} , Databases ^{150,152,154} , GTP
Lee (2025) ¹³⁷	23381	14183@10 μ M	Binary	GitHub	Studies ^{30,68,85,106} , ChEMBL, PubChem
Tran-Nguyen (2025) ¹⁴¹	299927	1937@20 μ M	Binary	GitHub	ChEMBL, PubChem
	2340	N/A	IC50		
Zhang (2025) ¹⁴⁴	13890	N/A	IC50	GitHub	Study ¹⁰⁸ , ChEMBL
Zhao (2026) ¹⁴⁶	15806	5965@1 μ M	Binary	GitHub	ChEMBL
References to databases and datasets: FenichelDB ¹⁵⁶ , PubChem ¹⁵² , QTDrugs ¹⁵⁷ , DrugBank ¹⁵⁸ , ChEMBL ¹⁵⁰ , Tox-Portal ¹⁵⁹ , WOMBAT ¹⁶⁰ , OCHEM ¹⁶¹ , hERGCentral ¹⁵³ , GOSTAR ¹⁵¹ , BindingDB ¹⁵⁴ , Tox21 ¹⁵⁵					
Annotations: [§] includes mixtures, [†] not all values available, [‡] multiple thresholds available, [¶] original link deprecated, a link to an updated version is given.					

1.3. Availability

Table S3. Summary of availability of data, code, model, and prediction platforms.

Study (Year)	Data	Code	Models	Platform	In-paper	Ref
Ponti (2001) ¹⁴⁷	Yes	No	No	No	Data	No
Cavalli (2002) ¹	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Pharmacophore	No
Ekins (2002) ²	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Pharmacophore	No
Roche (2002) ³	Partially	No	No	No	Data [†]	No
Ekins (2003) ⁴	No	No	No	No	No	No
Keserü (2003) ⁵	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Pearlstein (2003) ⁶	Yes	No	Partially	No	Data, Interactions	No
Aronov (2004) ⁸	No	No	Yes	No	Pharmacophore	No
Aptula (2004) ⁷	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Bains (2004) ⁹	Yes	No	Yes	No	Descriptors, Pharmacophore, Data	No
Fioravanzo (2004) ¹⁰	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Data	No
Cianchetta (2005) ¹¹	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	Data [†] , Pharmacophore	No
O'Brien (2005) ¹²	No	No	No	No	No	No
Tobita (2005) ¹³	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Descriptors	No
Aronov (2006) ¹⁴	No	No	Yes	No	Pharmacophore	No
Coi (2006) ¹⁵	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Dubus (2006) ¹⁶	No	No	Yes	No	Descriptors, Decision tree	No
Ekins (2006) ¹⁷	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Descriptors	No
Gepp (2006) ¹⁸	No	No	Yes	No	Decision tree, Descriptors	No
Seierstad (2006) ¹⁹	Partially	No	Partially	No	Data [†] , Descriptors	No
Sun (2006) ²⁰	Partially	No	Partially	No	Data [†] , Descriptors	No
Song (2006) ²¹	Partially	No	Partially	No	Data [†] , Fragments	No
Yoshida (2006) ²²	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Du (2007) ²³	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Leong (2007) ²⁴	Yes	No	Partially	No	Data, Pharmacophore	No
Obrezanova (2007) ²⁵	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Chekmarev (2008) ²⁶	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Gunturi (2008) ²⁷	Yes	No	Partially	No	Data, Descriptors	No
Jia (2008) ²⁸	Partially	No	No	No	Data [†]	No
Kramer (2008) ²⁹	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	Pharmacophore	No
Li (2008) ³⁰	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Thai [◊] (2008) ³¹	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Descriptors	No
Thai [◊] (2008) ³²	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Descriptors	No
Wang (2008) ³³	No	No	No	No	Descriptors	No
Coi (2009) ³⁴	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Equation	No
Ermondi (2009) ³⁵	Yes	No	No	No	Data	No
Hansen (2009) ³⁶	No	No	No	No	No	No
Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁷	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	No	No
Nisius [◊] (2009) ³⁸	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Thai (2009) ³⁹	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Doddareddy (2010) ⁴⁰	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	Fragments, Decision tree	No
Obrezanova (2010) ⁴¹	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Su (2010) ⁴²	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	Equation	No

Table S3 – continued from previous page

Study (Year)	Data	Code	Models	Platform	In-paper	Ref
Wiśniowska (2010) ⁴³	No	No	No	No	Descriptors	No
Cuny (2011) ⁴⁴	No	No	Partially	No	Descriptors, Pharmacophore, Equation	No
Kim (2011) ⁴⁵	No	No	No	No	Fragments	No
Obiol-Pardo (2011) ⁴⁶	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	No	No
Robinson (2011) ⁴⁷	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Descriptors	No
Sinha (2011) ⁴⁸	Yes	No	No	No	Data	No
Shen (2011) ⁴⁹	No	No	Partially	No	Descriptors	No
Broccatelli (2012) ⁵⁰	Yes (SI)	No	Partially	No	No	No
Kar (2012) ⁵¹	Yes (SI)	No	Yes	No	Equation	No
Polak (2012) ⁵²	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Hyperparameters	No
Tan (2012) ⁵³	Yes	No	Partially	No	Data, Equation	No
Wang (2012) ⁵⁴	Yes	No	Yes	No	Decision tree, Fragments	Data [¶]
Wiśniowska (2012) ⁵⁵	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Hyperparameters	No
Czodrowski (2013) ⁵⁶	Yes (SI)	Yes	No	No	Fragments	Code
Kireeva (2013) ⁵⁷	No	No	No	No	No	No
Braga (2014) ⁵⁸	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Data [¶] ; Platform [¶]
Kratz (2014) ⁵⁹	Partially	No	Yes	No	Data, Pharmacophore	No
Liu (2014) ⁶⁰	No	No	No	No	Fragments	No
Braga (2015) ⁶¹	Yes (Online)	No	No	Yes	No	Platform [¶]
Du (2015) ⁶²	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Ma (2015) ⁶³	No	No	Partially	No	Hyperparameters	No
Chavan (2016) ⁶⁴	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Didziapetris (2016) ⁶⁵	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Gobbi (2016) ⁶⁶	Yes	No	Partially	No	Equation	No
Sheridan (2016) ⁶⁷	No	No	No	No	No	No
Wang (2016) ⁶⁸	Yes (SI)	No	Yes	No	Decision tree, Pharmacophore	No
Zhang (2016) ⁶⁹	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Fragments	No
Chemi (2017) ⁷⁰	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Pharmacophore	No
Li (2017) ⁷¹	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Data, Model
Sun (2017) ⁷²	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Pharmacophore	No
Alves (2018) ⁷³	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Code*
Munawar (2018) ⁷⁴	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Interactions, Pharmacophore	No
Siramshetty (2018) ⁷⁵	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Wacker (2018) ⁷⁶	No	No	No	No	No	No
Yang (2018) ⁷⁷	No	No	No	Yes	No	Platform
Cai (2019) ⁷⁸	Yes (SI)	Yes	No	No	No	Code
Hu (2019) ⁷⁹	No	No	No	No	No	No
Konda (2019) ⁸⁰	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Lee (2019) ⁸¹	On Request	No	No	Yes	Features	Platform
Munawar (2019) ⁸²	No	No	No	No	Interactions	No
Negami (2019) ⁸³	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Ogura (2019) ⁸⁴	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Platform
Zhang (2019) ⁸⁵	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Choi (2020) ⁸⁶	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Khalifa (2020) ⁸⁷	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Kim (2020) ⁸⁸	No	No	No	No	No	No

Table S3 – continued from previous page

Study (Year)	Data	Code	Models	Platform	In-paper	Ref
Liu (2020) ⁸⁹	No	No	No	No	Fragments	No
Ryu (2020) ⁹⁰	Partially	No	Yes	No	No	Platform [¶]
Siramshetty (2020) ⁹¹	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Wang (2020) ⁹²	On Request	No	No	No	Algorithm, Parameters	No
Creanza (2021) ⁹³	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Interactions, Protein	No
Karim (2021) ⁹⁴	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Lee (2021) ⁹⁵	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Meng (2021) ⁹⁶	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Moorthy (2021) ⁹⁷	Yes (SI)	No	Yes	No	Fragments, Equation	No
Sato (2021) ⁹⁸	No	No	No	No	No	Platform [¶]
Stergiopoulos (2021) ⁹⁹	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Experimental, Equation	No
Wu (2021) ¹⁰⁰	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Xiong (2021) ¹⁰¹	No	No	No	Yes	No	Platform
Arab (2022) ¹⁰²	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Delre (2022) ¹⁰³	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Workflow
Ding (2022) ¹⁰⁴	Yes (SI)	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Ishihara (2022) ¹⁰⁵	No	No	No	No	No	No
Kim (2022) ¹⁰⁶	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Kong (2022) ¹⁰⁷	No	No	No	No	No	No
Krishna (2022) ¹⁰⁸	Yes (SI)	Yes	No	No	No	Code
Lanevskij (2022) ¹⁰⁹	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	No	No
Melnikov (2022) ¹¹⁰	No	No	No	No	No	No
Shan (2022) ¹¹¹	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Zhang (2022) ¹¹²	Yes (Online)	No	No	Yes	Fragments	Platform [¶]
Arab (2023) ¹¹³	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Banerjee (2023) ¹¹⁴	Yes (SI)	No	Yes	No	No	Model
Chen (2023) ¹¹⁵	Yes (SI)	No	No	No	Fragments	No
Das (2023) ¹¹⁶	Yes (SI)	No	Yes	No	Equation	No
Feng (2023) ¹¹⁷	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Wang [◊] (2023) ¹¹⁸	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Wang [◊] (2023) ¹¹⁹	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Vittorio (2023) ¹²⁰	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Data, Model
Ylipää (2023) ¹²¹	No	No	No	No	No	No
Arab (2024) ¹²²	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Chen (2024) ¹²³	No	No	No	Yes	Fragments	Platform
He (2024) ¹²⁴	Partially	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code; Model
Liu (2024) ¹²⁵	No	No	No	No	No	No
Sanches (2024) ¹²⁶	Yes (SI)	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Code; Platform
Wang (2024) ¹²⁷	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Code; Platform
Yang (2024) ¹²⁸	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Cano (2025) ¹²⁹	No	No	No	Yes	No	Platform
Feng (2025) ¹³⁰	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code; Model
Gambacorta (2025) ¹³¹	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Data, Code; Platform
Han (2025) ¹³²	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Hossain (2025) ¹³³	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Jin (2025) ¹³⁴	No	Yes	No	No	No	Code

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Study (Year)	Data	Code	Models	Platform	In-paper	Ref
Jing (2025) ¹³⁵	No	No	No	No	No	No
Kyro (2025) ¹³⁶	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Lee (2025) ¹³⁷	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Liu (2025) ¹³⁹	No	No	No	No	No	No
Liu (2025) ¹³⁸	No	Yes	No	No	No	Code
Mohammad (2025) ¹⁴⁰	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Tran-Nguyen (2025) ¹⁴¹	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Xu (2025) ¹⁴²	No	No	No	No	No	No
Yang (2025) ¹⁴³	No	Yes	No	No	No	Code
Zhang (2025) ¹⁴⁴	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Data, Code, Model
Chu (2026) ¹⁴⁵	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code
Zhao (2026) ¹⁴⁶	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Data, Code

Annotations: †not all values available, ¶original link deprecated, *unable to verify, °separate studies

2. Notes

Note S1. ChEMBL data extraction and curation Bioactivity data were retrieved from ChEMBL¹⁵⁰ (version 36) for all assays in which at least one assigned gene corresponded to a CiPA cardiac ion channel target. Assay-level filtering excluded assays corresponding to mutant proteins, assays where the channel gene originated from a non-mammalian species, ambiguous target assignments (e.g., protein families), assays with a confidence score below 6, and assays measuring channel activation, opening, or agonist activity. Measurement-level filtering removed entries with invalid or ambiguous activity comments and non-standard endpoint types. For quantitative measurements (IC₅₀, K_i, K_d), entries outside the range of 4–11 pX units were excluded. For single-concentration inhibition data, only values within –20% to 100% were retained; values below –20% were considered potential channel activators and excluded. Compound counts reflect unique ChEMBL molecule IDs per channel and should be treated as upper bounds, as study-specific curation, structure standardisation, and deduplication will further reduce the number of compounds available for model training.

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